

Molecular Detection of *Coccidiosis* in Poultry Farms in Abeokuta and Environs

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Abstract

Coccidiosis is a major parasitic disease of poultry, causing significant economic losses and threatening food security. Despite prophylactic drug use, outbreaks remain common in tropical regions, including Nigeria. A total of 111 fecal samples were collected from 70 layer and 41 broiler flocks across poultry farms in Abeokuta and environs, Ogun State. Samples were examined using flotation microscopy, and positive samples were subjected to PCR amplification of the ITS-1 region for species identification. Statistical analysis was performed using chi-square tests. Microscopy revealed *Eimeria* oocysts in 71.2% of samples, with infection rates of 78.6% in layers and 58.5% in broilers. PCR confirmed four pathogenic species: *E. maxima* (200 bp), *E. praecox* (272 bp), *E. mitis* (327 bp), and *E. tenella* (540 bp). No significant association was found between prevalence and flock type ($\chi^2 = 6.134$, $P = 0.541$). In conclusion, the high infection rates observed despite prophylactic treatment suggest possible drug tolerance and widespread subclinical coccidiosis. Ogun State is endemic for multiple *Eimeria* species, underscoring the need for improved control strategies.

Keyword: Poultry, Food security, Coccidiosis, *Eimeria*

Introduction

Chicken meat is one of the most affordable and accessible sources of animal protein. It is low in fat, widely acceptable across cultures, and contributes to food and nutrition security (Islam et al., 2022). Poultry farming also has a relatively low environmental footprint

compared with other livestock systems, producing fewer greenhouse gas emissions and serving as a more sustainable agricultural enterprise. The sector contributes substantially to job creation and poverty reduction, particularly in developing countries, where poultry production

represents a major share of meat production and supports household income and national economic development. Poultry products, especially eggs, are rich in high-quality protein, amino acids, minerals, and vitamins, and they help address growth-related nutritional deficiencies in children. The nutritional value of chicken and chicken products has therefore been linked to improved dietary quality and reduced malnutrition in vulnerable populations.

Despite these advantages, poultry production remains constrained by several challenges, including disease outbreaks, parasitic infections, and inadequate funding. Among these challenges, coccidiosis, an endemic enteric disease common in tropical and subtropical regions, is one of the most important. The development and spread of its causative agents are favoured by ecological and management conditions throughout the year. Coccidiosis reduces growth, suppresses immune function, and can cause high mortality, resulting in global economic losses that exceed US\$3 billion annually through reduced productivity and increased treatment and prevention costs. The estimated global economic burden of coccidiosis has increased sharply, rising from about \$0.8 billion in 2002 to approximately £10.4 billion in 2016 and reaching £12.9 billion at its peak in 2022, driven by the growth of the global chicken population and the gradual shift away from antibiotic use in poultry production.

Coccidiosis is caused by protozoan parasites in the genus *Eimeria*, within the phylum Apicomplexa, and the genus includes more than 1,000 species. Outbreaks have been reported across multiple continents, including Iran, Egypt, Ethiopia, South Africa (Mwale and Masika, 2011), and Nigeria. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis of 41 studies estimated the global pooled prevalence of *Eimeria* in domestic chickens at 44.3%, with the highest prevalence in humid subtropical regions. Clinically,

chicken coccidiosis caused by pathogenic *Eimeria* species is characterized by dysentery, enteritis, and diarrhoea, which may be bloody. Infected birds may also show emaciation, poor feed conversion, delayed sexual maturity, drooping wings, reduced growth, and decreased egg production. If untreated, the disease can cause high morbidity and mortality and remains a major threat to poultry production, affecting both economic performance and animal welfare. *Eimeria* species infect different regions of the intestinal tract by destroying epithelial cells, causing inflammation, increased intestinal permeability, impaired nutrient absorption, reduced growth, and greater susceptibility to secondary infections such as necrotic enteritis. Among these species, *E. tenella* is generally regarded as the most widespread and virulent, and a recent meta-analysis identified it as the most prevalent species globally, with a pooled prevalence of 38.7%. Accurate identification of *Eimeria* species is therefore essential for effective diagnosis and disease control, and it is particularly relevant to epidemiologists, drug developers, and vaccine researchers. Transmission occurs through ingestion of sporulated oocysts, which birds acquire by pecking at contaminated litter or consuming contaminated feed and water. Wet litter and high stocking density in poorly managed intensive systems can further worsen disease expression (Sharma et al., 2015).

Several methods have been used to diagnose coccidiosis, including histopathological examination of necropsy samples, post-mortem lesion scoring, microscopic lesion scoring, and microscopic examination of parasites in mucosal scrapings from the small intestine. However, conventional diagnostic methods can be subjective and time-consuming, which has encouraged the development of molecular approaches for more specific and reliable detection. Advances in molecular diagnostics have

opened new possibilities for parasitic disease detection, with molecular markers capable of distinguishing *Eimeria* species even from small numbers of oocysts. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) offers a practical and unified identification method that can detect several *Eimeria* species individually or simultaneously in a single reaction, enabling rapid and efficient diagnosis. More recently, highly sensitive assays such as multiplex TaqMan-MGB real-time PCR have achieved detection limits as low as 10^1 to 10^2 DNA copies/ μ L, further improving diagnostic precision. This study, therefore, aimed to detect and characterize *Eimeria* species using both microscopic and molecular methods and to determine the prevalence of coccidiosis in selected poultry farms in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Study area

The study was conducted in Ogun State, a southwestern state in Nigeria commonly known as the “gateway state.” Ogun State has an estimated population of 6.34 million (City Population, 2025) and covers an area of 16,762 km². The state has a humid tropical climate and two main vegetation zones: tropical rainforest and guinea savanna. The main occupations of the inhabitants are farming and trading, with crops such as banana, vegetables, pepper, and pineapple, as well as tree and cash crops including oil palm and cocoa. The Ogun State Agricultural Development Programme (OGADEP) is administratively divided into four zones. Samples were collected from poultry farms in five locations: Ijebu Igbo, Odeda, Mile 6, Ijebu Ode, and Aro Local Government Areas (Figure 1).

Sample size determination

The required sample size was estimated using the formula described by Thrusfield (1997):

$$n = z^2pq / d^2$$

where n = required sample size, z = standard normal deviate (1.96 at 95% confidence

level), p = expected prevalence, $q = 1 - p$, and d = desired precision (0.05). Using a prevalence of 14% as previously reported by Adamu et al. (2009), the minimum required sample size was calculated as 185 chickens. A total of 111 fecal samples were collected.

Sample collection

Fecal samples were collected from 111 poultry farms in the study area. Farms were selected by random sampling from the membership register of the local poultry farmers’ association. From each farm, fecal samples from approximately two birds were randomly selected and pooled to form a composite sample, yielding a total of 111 samples from 70 layer flocks and 41 broiler flocks. Samples were collected in sterile Ziploc bags and transported in a cooler with ice packs to the Veterinary Parasitology Laboratory, College of Veterinary Medicine, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, for immediate analysis.

Microscopic detection of *Eimeria* oocysts

Fecal samples were examined for *Eimeria* oocysts using the simple flotation technique described by Long et al. (1976). One gram of each sample was emulsified in 100 mL of distilled water in a flat-bottom conical flask and filtered through gauze to remove debris. The filtrate was transferred to a 10 mL test tube, filling approximately one-third of the tube, and the remainder was filled with saturated sodium chloride solution (specific gravity 1.18–1.20). A cover slip was placed on the convex meniscus and left for 15 minutes. It was then removed vertically, placed on a clean glass slide, and examined under a light microscope at $\times 10$, $\times 40$, and $\times 100$ magnifications.

Samples positive for *Eimeria* oocysts were graded according to Lawal et al. (2008): +1 (1–10 oocysts per field), +2 (11–20 oocysts per field), and +3 (>20 oocysts per field). Samples graded +2 and +3 were selected for molecular analysis.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area

Fecal oocyst load determination

Oocyst density in positive samples was quantified using a modified McMaster counting technique. One gram of fecal material was emulsified in 15 mL of distilled water and sieved to remove debris. The filtrate was transferred to a 15 mL centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 2,000 rpm for 2 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and the sediment was resuspended to the original volume with saturated sodium chloride flotation solution (specific gravity 1.18–1.20). The tubes were inverted several times to ensure uniform mixing, and both chambers of a McMaster slide were filled using a fine-tipped glass pipette. After standing for 15 minutes, the oocysts were counted in both

chambers. The total count was multiplied by 50 to obtain oocysts per gram of feces (OPG).

Genomic DNA extraction

Microscopy-positive fecal samples with oocyst grades of +2 or above were subjected to DNA extraction. Samples were homogenized and sieved, and 100 μ L of the resulting suspension was transferred to 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and centrifuged at 1,000 rpm for 3 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and genomic DNA was extracted from the pellet using the AccuPrep® Stool DNA Extraction Kit (Bioneer, Republic of Korea) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 400 μ L of stool lysis buffer and 20 μ L of proteinase K were added, and the mixture was vortexed for 2 minutes and incubated at 60°C for 10 minutes. After

centrifugation at 12,000 rpm for 5 minutes, the supernatant was transferred to a new tube containing binding buffer, incubated again at 60°C for 10 minutes, and mixed with 100 µL of isopropanol. The solution was passed through a silica-binding column by centrifugation at 8,000 rpm for 1 minute. The column was washed sequentially with 500 µL each of Washing Buffer 1 and Washing Buffer 2, with centrifugation at 8,000 rpm for 1 minute after each wash. The column was then dried by centrifugation at 12,000 rpm for 1 minute. DNA was eluted with 50 µL of elution buffer after a 5-minute incubation at room temperature and centrifugation at 13,000 rpm for 1 minute. Extracted DNA was stored at -20°C until further analysis.

PCR amplification and species identification

The internal transcribed spacer 1 (ITS-1) region of ribosomal DNA was selected as the molecular marker because of its high discriminatory power for *Eimeria* species identification. The ITS-1 locus shows substantial interspecific variability while remaining relatively conserved within species, allowing reliable differentiation of closely related *Eimeria* taxa. Unlike highly conserved markers such as 18S rRNA, which are more suitable for genus-level identification, ITS-1 supports species-level resolution using conventional PCR. In addition, the ITS-1 region allows rapid identification based on species-specific amplicon size polymorphisms, making it suitable for routine diagnostics in resource-limited settings.

The ITS-1 region was amplified using the generic primer pair ITS1F (5'-AAGTTGCGTAAATAGAGCCCTC-3') and ITS1R (5'-AGACATCCATTGCTGAAAG-3'), which produces species-specific amplicon sizes for different *Eimeria* species (Schnitzler et al., 1998; Lien et al., 2007). The optimal annealing temperature was determined by

gradient PCR using DNA extracted from a microscopy-positive sample, yielding an optimal temperature of 56.7°C.

PCR amplification was performed in a Personal Thermocycler (Bio-Rad Inc., Hercules, CA, USA) in a final reaction volume of 25 µL containing 12.5 µL of 2× PCR master mix (New England BioLabs, USA), 0.5 µL each of the forward and reverse primers (Bioneer Inc., South Korea), 2 µL of template DNA (~20 ng), and 7.5 µL of nuclease-free water. A positive control consisting of synthetic target DNA (gBlocks™ Gene Fragment, Integrated DNA Technologies, USA) and a no-template negative control were included in each PCR run.

The thermocycling conditions were as follows: initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes; 40 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 60 seconds, annealing at 56.7°C for 60 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 60 seconds; and a final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes. PCR products (10 µL) were resolved by electrophoresis on a 1.5% agarose gel prepared in 1× TAE buffer at 90 V for 60 minutes, alongside 10 µL of a 100 bp DNA ladder (Quanti-Marker, BioExpress, Kaysville, UT, USA). After electrophoresis, gels were stained with ethidium bromide and visualized under UV transillumination using a gel documentation system. Species identification was based on amplicon size: *Eimeria maxima* (~200 bp), *Eimeria praecox* (~272 bp), *Eimeria mitis* (~327 bp), and *Eimeria tenella* (~540 bp).

Statistical analysis

Data were organized and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics (version 21.0). Prevalence was calculated as the proportion of positive samples out of the total number examined and expressed as a percentage. The chi-square (χ^2) test was used to assess the association between *Eimeria* infection prevalence and flock type (layers

versus broilers). Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Prevalence of Eimeria infection according to flock type

Table 1 shows the prevalence of Eimeria infection according to flock type in the study

area. Of the 70-layer flocks sampled, 78.6% were infected with Eimeria, whereas 58.5% of the 41 broiler flocks were positive. The chi-square test indicated no statistically significant association between infection prevalence and flock type ($\chi^2 = 6.134$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.541$).

Table 1: Prevalence of *Eimeria* infection in the study area according to flock type

Flock type	Number sampled	Number positive (%)
Layers	70	55 (78.6)
Broilers	41	24 (58.5)
Total	111	79 (71.2)

Plate1: Sporulated oocyst at x 100 objective

Plate2: Sporulated oocyst at x 40 objective

Plate3: Sporulated oocyst at x 10

Plate4: Sporulated oocyst at x 40

Figure 2: Gel electrophoresis of amplified *Eimeria* DNA.

Microscopic detection of *Eimeria* oocysts

Various forms and shapes of *Eimeria* oocysts were detected by microscopy (Figures 1–4). In total, 79 samples (71.2%) were positive for *Eimeria* oocysts, whereas 32 samples (28.8%) were negative.

Molecular detection of *Eimeria* spp.

Gel electrophoresis of the PCR products revealed bands of 200 bp, 272 bp, 327 bp, and 540 bp, corresponding to *E. maxima*, *E. praecox*, *E. mitis*, and *E. tenella*, respectively (Figure 2). PCR analysis showed that all samples positive by microscopy were also positive by PCR. In total, 85 samples were positive for *Eimeria* spp. by PCR.

Discussion

The high prevalence of *Eimeria* infection (71.2%) observed in this study confirms that coccidiosis remains a major constraint to poultry production in the study area. This finding is consistent with recent global reports showing that *Eimeria* infections remain widespread in intensive poultry systems, especially in tropical and subtropical regions where environmental conditions favor oocyst survival and

transmission. The resilience of *Eimeria* oocysts, which can persist in moist litter for extended periods, combined with high stocking density, likely contributes to sustained transmission across farms.

The prevalence reported here is higher than values documented in some recent regional studies, such as those reporting prevalence of about 58% in India, but it is broadly consistent with reports of widespread farm-level infection and mixed-species circulation in Africa and Asia. These differences may reflect variation in farm management, climate, sampling strategy, and diagnostic method. Studies using molecular tools such as ITS1-PCR often report higher detection rates than microscopy alone because of their greater sensitivity and ability to detect low-level infections.

The detection of multiple *Eimeria* species, namely *E. maxima*, *E. praecox*, *E. mitis*, and *E. tenella*, is consistent with the current understanding that mixed infections are common in poultry production systems. Molecular studies have shown that co-infections involving two or more *Eimeria* species are frequent, with some reports

identifying mixed infections in more than 80% of samples. This has important implications because interactions among species may influence pathogenicity, immune responses, and treatment outcomes. At the same time, the present study identified fewer species than some reports that detected six or seven species in similar settings. This difference may reflect methodological constraints, including selective PCR testing and reliance on amplicon size for species identification, which may limit detection of less abundant or genetically divergent species.

The higher prevalence observed in layer flocks than in broilers is consistent with established epidemiological patterns. Layers are generally reared for longer periods, which increases cumulative exposure to infective oocysts and encourages environmental build-up. However, the absence of a statistically significant association between flock type and infection prevalence suggests that coccidiosis is widely distributed across production systems. This supports evidence that management practices, rather than production type alone, are the main determinants of infection dynamics.

An important observation in this study is the detection of *Eimeria* in apparently healthy flocks. This finding supports the growing recognition that subclinical coccidiosis is common and often overlooked in commercial poultry systems. Although subclinical infections may not produce obvious clinical signs, they can significantly impair nutrient absorption, feed efficiency, and growth performance, thereby contributing to hidden economic losses. This emphasizes the limitation of relying solely on clinical signs for disease surveillance.

The continued detection of *Eimeria* despite routine prophylactic use of anticoccidial drugs raises concern. Although this may suggest reduced drug efficacy or emerging resistance, caution is needed in interpreting

this finding, because resistance was not directly evaluated in the present study. Recent literature indicates that resistance to commonly used anticoccidials is increasingly reported worldwide, largely because of prolonged and indiscriminate drug use. However, other factors, including incorrect dosing, poor biosecurity, and inadequate litter management, may also contribute to persistent infections.

From a methodological perspective, the use of ITS-1 PCR enabled species-level identification and improved diagnostic sensitivity compared with microscopy. Nevertheless, recent advances in molecular diagnostics, particularly multiplex real-time PCR, offer greater sensitivity and the ability to quantify parasite load, detect mixed infections more accurately, and reduce false negatives. The reliance on conventional PCR and selective sampling in the present study may therefore have limited the completeness of species detection and underestimated infection complexity.

A further limitation is that only samples with moderate to high oocyst counts (+2 and above) were subjected to molecular analysis. This approach may have introduced selection bias by excluding low-intensity infections and could therefore underrepresent less abundant or subclinical *Eimeria* species while overrepresenting dominant species in the study area. In addition, species identification based solely on amplicon size carries some risk of misclassification because of possible size overlap or nonspecific amplification, especially in the absence of sequencing confirmation. Conventional PCR is also qualitative and does not provide information on parasite load or the relative abundance of species in mixed infections. Variation in DNA extraction efficiency, particularly because of the resistant nature of *Eimeria* oocyst walls, may also affect detection sensitivity across samples. Despite these limitations, the findings remain

valuable for understanding the distribution of major pathogenic *Eimeria* species in the study area. Future studies should include all samples regardless of microscopy results, use quantitative PCR for better sensitivity and quantification, and validate species identity through sequencing or additional genetic markers.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated a high prevalence of *Eimeria* infection in poultry farms in Ogun State, Nigeria, based on microscopic and molecular detection. Molecular analysis using the ITS-1 marker confirmed the presence of four *Eimeria* species: *E. maxima*, *E. praecox*, *E. mitis*, and *E. tenella*, indicating that multiple pathogenic species are circulating in the study area. Although higher prevalence was recorded in layer flocks, no statistically significant association was observed between infection prevalence and flock type. These findings show that coccidiosis is widespread in the study area and that mixed-species infections are common under field conditions. The detection of infection in apparently healthy flocks suggests the presence of subclinical coccidiosis, which may affect productivity. However, the persistence of infection despite reported prophylactic use of anticoccidial drugs may reflect reduced efficacy or management-related factors, although this was not directly assessed in the present study and should therefore be interpreted with caution. Overall, the results highlight the need for improved surveillance and integrated control strategies, including better farm hygiene, optimized anticoccidial use, and consideration of vaccination programs. Further studies incorporating quantitative and molecular validation approaches are recommended to better understand infection dynamics and resistance patterns.

Conflict of Interest

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the publication.

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